

USE OF PRAKRITI AS A MARKER IN PREDICTION OF NATURE OF FUTURE DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is one of the oldest health sciences of the world that believes in the maintaining the health of a healthy individual prior to the treatment of diseases. With the concepts of *tridoshas* and *prakriti* being its core philosophies, it paves the ways for not only personalized medicine and treatment but also personalized prevention. *Prakriti* is unique psychosomatic temperament of an individual encompassing his/her physical, functional and behavioural characteristics. Thus every person has his/her own unique constitution which governs their metabolism, response to environmental factors, drugs and also susceptibility to diseases. With emerging advanced concepts like *ayurgenomics* evidences has surfaced connecting the concepts of *tridosha* and *prakriti* with metabolic pathway, chronic diseases and phenotypic representation of certain genotypes of individuals. A benefit to such discoveries can be the possibility of new borns being screened for their *prakriti* by genetic testing which will enable the prevention of various

future diseases for such children through the implementation of various dietary and lifestyle regimens from an early age that is suitable for each *prakriti*. e.g : *Vata Prakriti* individuals are more prone to disorders such as neurological issues, arthritis and other painful conditions. *Pitta Prakriti* individuals are susceptible to inflammatory conditions like skin rashes, hypertension, ulcers and digestive problems. *Kapha Prakriti* experiences problems of feeling of heaviness, congestion, obesity, respiratory problems and diabetes, etc. Hence one should avoid diet and activities that enhances gunas of the one's respective prakriti and follow the diet and regimens opposite to the prakriti of the person. Such preventive implementation will take the society one step further in leading a healthy and productive life.

KEYWORDS: tridoshas, prakriti, ayurgenomics.

INTRODUCTION

A good physician knows individual variations and specific treatment accordingly. - Charaka Samhita *Prakriti* of an individual is a distinct phenotype that is characterised by physical, psychological, physiological and behavioural characteristics. It is an unique concept of Ayurveda that aims at personalised prevention and treatment of diseases which cannot be found in any other contemporary system of medicine.

“शुक्रशोणितसंयोगे यो भवेद्वेष उत्कटः । प्रकृतिर्जायते तेन ॥” [shu.sha.4/63]

According to *Acharya Sushruta*, formation of *Prakriti* takes place by the prominence of *Tridosha* at the time of union of *Shukra* (sperm) and *Shonita* (ovum) in the *Garbhashaya* (womb) of mother. *Prakriti* is created due to the dominance of any one, two, or all of the three *Vatadi* doshas (*Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*) and *Satvadi* (*satva*, *raja* and *tama*) *Manas Gunas*.

“जन्ममरणान्तरालभाविनी अविकारणी दोषास्थिती प्रकृति ॥” [Rasavaishashika]

According to the quotation from *Acharya* above, *Prakriti*—the *Doshik* constitution that was there at birth remains constant for an individual throughout his/her life from birth till death.

The *prakriti* of a person is influenced by a combination of genetic and acquired factors. Genetic constitution is determined by the fusion of *Shukra* and *Shonita* whereas the acquired constitution is shaped by environmental factors such as age, race, season, geographical location etc.

Factors influencing the Prakriti

Garbhakalaja bhava ^[1]	Jatiprasaktadi bhava ^[2]
Sukra- Shonita prakriti	Jatiprasakta bhava
Kala- Garbhashaya prakriti	Kulaprasakta bhava
Maturaharvihara prakriti	Desha anupatini prakriti Kala anupatini prakriti
Mahabhutavikara prakriti	Vayo anupatini prakriti Pratyatmaniyata prakriti

Types of prakriti

Sharirika Prakriti ^[1]	Manasika Prakriti ^[3]
Vataja Pittaja Kaphaja Vata-pittaj Vata-kaphaja Pitta-kaphaja Vata- pitta- kaphaja	Satvika Rajasik Tamasika (according to acharya Charaka, 16 types of manasik prakriti exists) ^[4]

METHODS

The current study has been founded on a careful assessment of traditional knowledge, published research articles, contemporary literature and research projects carried out at various institutions. A systematic presentation of the potential association between the *prakriti* of a person and diseases that are most likely to occur in them based on the status of *tridoshas* has been carried out in this presentation.

DISCUSSION

Since *prakriti* is related to certain physical and mental tendencies that determine susceptibility to diseases, the ancient texts of Ayurveda also provide guidelines for maintaining lifestyles in accordance with one's *prakriti* for continued healthy living in a personalized manner. Therefore, proper determination of *Prakriti* of a person becomes essential for maintaining a healthy lifestyle. There exist a number of tools, mainly questionnaires, for ascertaining the *prakriti* of an individual and there have been ongoing attempts of validating such a tool. In addition to this, a number of research work has also been carried out to invent techniques that can establish the scientific basis of *prakriti* assessment in the light of modern science.

In the recent times, many researches have been carried out about the association of the *tridosha* theory with living systems of all organisms, biological functions in cells and organisms, and genetics.^[6] One such area with respect to modern science in which some

evidence is being generated is now known as *Ayugenomics*. The basic concept behind *Ayugenomics* is the fact that if the system of *tridosha* is prevalent in all organisms then there must be ways in which it is inherited. Stated simply, *prakriti* must be a phenotypic phenomenon arising from a particular genotype.^[7]

Recently, a study reported that body mass index (BMI) in *vata-pitta prakriti* individuals was significantly less as compared to *kapha-pitta prakriti* and the *vata-pitta prakriti* individuals were found to be having maximum platelet aggregation.^[8] One of the associations of *tridoshas* has been hypothesized by Hankey (2005) in which it was suggested that the peptide coenzyme A, which occurs in all cells across all species-preserved through evolution and is associated with lipid metabolism, is linked with the *tridoshas* at the cellular level. Based on the properties of the three body types, the predominance of *kaphaja* body types for gaining weight is quite well known. This propensity to gain weight and for obesity is in turn linked with a number of chronic diseases such as heart disease, hypertension, and diabetes; all of which are increasingly viewed collectively as metabolic syndrome. Similarly looking at the properties of *pittaja* body type it can be predicted that such individuals can have a propensity to develop ulcers, bleeding disorders, and skin disorders more common. *Vataja* body types can have propensity to develop neurological problems, dementia, movement and speech disorders, arrhythmias, and related chronic diseases as well. However, of the three body types, classical texts suggest that *vata* type individuals will have maximum propensity for chronic disease.

Studies show that biomarkers of coronary artery disease (CAD) such as very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) and low-density lipoproteins (LDL) were significantly higher; while high-density lipoprotein (HDL) was significantly lower among CAD patients who were *vata kapha* (VK) when compared to other body types. VK body type was also significantly correlated with diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and dyslipidemia with highest levels of inflammatory markers such as IL6, TNF alpha, hsCRP, and HOMA IR. These inflammatory markers were also found to be higher in *kaphaja* body type. Thus, the patterns of association that might be expected from Ayurvedic *tridosha theory* have been shown to have clear links with certain chronic disease conditions.^[9]

Joint research being carried out with Ayurveda and current sciences is entering novel territory every day. Various research work can be seen being carried out to establish relationships between *prakriti* and genetics. One such research work has demonstrated a significant

correlation between various alleles of human leukocyte antigen (HLA) genotype and prakriti providing rationale and preliminary experimental support for the concept of an association between HLA alleles and Ayurvedic *tridosha* theory of individual *prakriti* types.^[10]

Common lifestyle diseases and type of Prakriti most prone for some disorders^[5]

Sr.no	Lifestyle disorder	Correlated Ayurvedic condition	Most prone Prakriti
1.	Atherosclerosis	Dhamanipratichaya	Kapha and Vata
2.	Alzheimer's disease	Smriti bhramsa	Kapha and Vata
3.	Some types of cancer	Granthi and Arbuda	Kapha
4.	Asthma	Shwasa	Kapha
5.	Liver cirrhosis	Kamala	Vata and Pitta
6.	Type 2 diabetes	Prameha	Kapha and vata
7.	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Shwasa roga	Kapha
8.	Heart disease	Hridaya roga	Kapha and pitta
9.	Metabolic syndrome	Agnimandya, amlapitta, aruchi and grahani	Kapha and pitta
10.	Chronic renal failure	Mutra roga	Kapha and vata
11.	Osteoporosis	Asthisushirata	Vata and pitta
12.	Depression	Avasada	Vata and pitta
13.	Obesity	Sthoulya	kapha

Aspect of prakriti determination at birth: Ayurvedic method of *prakriti* classification has led scientists to identify biochemical and gene expression differences among normal individuals—something which is not possible in western system of medicine. Thus, it can be anticipated that in near future genotype ascertainment can be used a predictive markers for prakriti.

RESULT

Thus it is well understood that at a person's *prakriti* is considered to be normal for that person when the *tridoshas* are in a state of equilibrium and any derangement in them leads to disease. As such, the job of an ayurvedic physician is to fulfil the prime aim of Ayurveda “*swasthaya swastha rakshanam*” i.e maintaining the health of an healthy individual. This can be achieved only when we know the *prakriti* of the individual and advice the regimens for *Ahara* and *Vihara* according to his/her *doshik* constitution and surrounding environment. Therefore, screening an individual to detect his/her *prakriti* at the earliest can have very significant and far-reaching implications. Knowing the *prakriti* of a child can help in inculcation lifestyles and food habits that will help in prevention of chronic diseases and improve quality of life for that individual. For example, if it is known that a child is of

kaphaja prakriti then right from the beginning the child can be encouraged to participate in sports and physical activity since kapha prakriti persons have a natural tendency for reduced movement. This will help the person to lead a healthier life and will prevent most of the chronic diseases related to obesity that a *kaphaja* person is otherwise susceptible to. Similarly, if it known that a child has *pitta prakriti*, steps can be taken right from childhood to make sure such a child inculcates habits that make him more patient and not lose his temper. In addition, spicy or acidic food may not be served to such a child since *pitta prakriti* individuals have more propensities to develop gastric ulcers and related disorders.

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